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HIGHLIGHTS

- This study presents a new daylight fluctuations control system for closed spaces.
- When the solar irradiance is very high, the current systems are not valid.
- A new control algorithm is proposed based on a low cost microcontroller.
- Tests performed in the laboratory on the system have shown positive results.

New daylight fluctuation control in a daylight system

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Abstract

Daylighting systems have recently been developed as another way to harness solar energy and contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Various technologies can be used in daylighting systems. These technologies differ with respect to the sunlight collection systems and sunlight transmission systems they employ, but have solar luminaires in common. Many factors, such as the fluctuations in the intensity of solar irradiance, limit the efficiency of daylighting systems. When the intensity of solar irradiance is very high, the current daylight-linked control systems are not valid. This study presents the design, construction and assessment of a daylight fluctuations control for enclosed spaces with no access to daylight from side openings. A new control algorithm is proposed for this purpose based on daylighting monitoring and a low cost microcontroller. It also allows communication between several solar luminaires based on long range wireless solutions. The main components of the proposed daylight fluctuation control are: the luminaire, mirror, shaft, frame, stepper motor driver, stepper motor, light sensor, limit switch, XBee and microcontroller. The system uses solar luminaries and dimmable lamps. Tests performed in the laboratory on the system have shown positive results. The different dimming profiles perceived have a linear zone; hence, the perceived changes in brightness are correct. The Just Noticeable Difference is less than 200.

direct

meaningless

Keywords:

Daylighting system, Daylight fluctuation, Daylighting control, Dimming profiles perceived

1. Introduction

Different international organizations, such as the International Energy Agency (*IEA*), have compiled data on trends in energy consumption worldwide. Lighting represents about 19% of global electricity consumption [1]. This study shows that global demand for artificial light has grown over the last decade at an average rate of 2.4% per annum. It also shows that 133 petalumen-hours (*Plmh*) of electric light were consumed in 2005 worldwide, at an average of 20 megalumen-hours (*Mlmh*) of light per person. For example, lighting is the leading energy consumer in office buildings. It represents 30% to 40% of the total energy consumption in office buildings [1]. Different strategies have been proposed to reduce the energy consumption of lighting systems [2] that can be summarized in the following points: ensuring that building codes promote the use of natural light and include minimum energy performance standards (*MEPS*) for lighting systems, as well as adopting lighting quality, reliability and *MEPS* for new and existing lighting products. The latest *IEA* estimates show that total potential energy savings in residential and services lighting could reach more than 2.4 exajoules (*EJ*) per annum by 2030 [2].

Daylight-linked controls represent a very useful strategy to optimize daylighting and consequently achieve substantial energy savings [3], [4].

The utilization of daylight in buildings has been studied primarily emphasizing energy saving potentials, but the health benefits associated with the use of daylighting have been addressed in a large number of publications [5], [6], [7], the amount of illuminance and light quality being regarded as factors defining a healthy environment. However, a lack of sufficient daylight may lead to a series of symptoms such as stress, mental fatigue and seasonal affective disorder. In contrast, an excessive amount of daylight may cause discomfort glare.

Several studies have shown that daylight may affect the level of mental fatigue and stress [8]. For many people, low levels of daylight can lead to seasonal affective disorder (*SAD*) [9]. *SAD* is a mood disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of major depression occurring with a seasonal pattern [10]. Exposure to natural light has been found to be effective in the treatment of *SAD* [11].

Discomfort glare is a major problem for the daylighting design of workspaces [12]. There are empirical formulas to predict the occurrence and magnitude of discomfort glare [13]. Discomfort glare presents a continuous range of in-

Fig. 1. Schematic of a daylighting system.

There are several types of sunlight collectors: parabolic dishes, parabolic troughs, Fresnel lenses and small scale linear Fresnel reflectors. A parabolic dish system consists of mirrors collected assembled on a supporting structure to reflect and concentrate solar radiation on the focus of the parabolic dish [17]. In a parabolic trough system, sunlight is concentrated through a concave parabolic reflector plate into a optical fiber. The optical fiber is permanently fixed to the focus of the parabolic concentrator to collect reflected light [18]. Fresnel lenses refract incident sunlight to a single focal point behind the

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9 opposite side of the lens, where an optical fiber bundle is mounted [19].
10 Small-scale linear Fresnel reflectors use stretched rows of mirrors to focus
11 incident solar radiation onto an optical fiber bundle that runs longitudinally
12 above the rows of mirrors located on a common focal line of the mirrors [20].
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14 Sunlight transmission systems can use several devices to transmit sunlight
15 to the inside of buildings: large-core optical fibers, optical fiber bundles [19]
16 and hollow-core reflective light-pipes [21]. The transmission of sunlight via
17 optical fiber is a flexible solution for daylighting systems and has some ad-
18 vantages such as the exclusion of the ultraviolet rays and, more importantly,
19 infrared rays.
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22 Sunlight propagation inside an optical fiber is unidirectional and can be
23 described using skew and meridional rays [22]. Due to the unidirectional
24 propagation of sunlight propagation, the system for illuminating a workspace
25 is designed in such a way that each optical fiber bundle behind an optical
26 element will diffuse the sunlight at a uniform illumination level. This type of
27 system is efficient, as all emitted sunlight is directly focused onto the work
28 surface. Therefore, a solar luminaire is an optical element designed to diffuse
29 sunlight emitted from an optical fiber bundle with a uniform illuminance
30 level on the working plane. Solar luminaires constitute sensitive elements in
31 daylighting systems as the effective use of natural light inside buildings de-
32 pends on them. The main characteristics that solar luminaires have to fulfill
33 are those of [23]: (i) maximizing the use of available light, (ii) minimizing
34 glare, and (iii) providing uniform illuminance levels on the work surface. So-
35 lar luminaires may be classified as passive or hybrid. Passive solar luminaires
36 are designed to be used only when adequate direct sunlight can be collected.
37 Hybrid solar luminaires are designed to be used continuously regardless of
38 the presence of direct sunlight, as they are associated with dimmable electric
39 lamps and a light sensor. A solar luminaire is made of materials such as
40 purified silica glass or a synthetic polymer called Poly(methyl methacrylate)
41 or *PMMA*. The efficiency of this system can be around 80% [24].
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48 As the very high intensity of collected sunlight can cause discomfort glare,
49 the main objective of this paper is to design an automatic control system
50 capable of rapidly adjusting the high intensity of collected sunlight. Further-
51 more, as a low intensity of collected sunlight can cause insufficient illumina-
52 tion, this paper also aims to supplement natural light with electric lamps. If
53 the electric light levels continuously change to adapt themselves to daylight
54 variations, also can cause discomfort glare. The low cost of the proposed
55 control system is another of the goals of the study. The performance of the
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9 daylight fluctuation control has been analyzed through laboratory tests in
10 order to evaluate its efficiency.

11 The paper is organized as follows. The statement of the problem, the
12 elements and the algorithms are presented in Section 2. Section 3 presents
13 the results of the study. The implementation of the system is presented in
14 Section 4, while Section 5 summarizes the main contributions and conclusions
15 of the paper.
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18 **2. Materials and methods**

19 *2.1. Problem statement*

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23 Various daylight-linked control technologies have been developed to utilize
24 daylight as an additional light source in indoor space. The types of daylight-
25 linked control are [25]: daylight-linked switching and daylight-linked dim-
26 ming. In the former, the electric lights are controlled by switching between
27 ‘on’ and ‘off’ according to the available daylight. In the latter, a dimming
28 system continuously controls the electric lamp output using a dimmable elec-
29 tronic ballast. Various studies have analyzed the daylight fluctuations and
30 the effects on the functioning of different daylight-linked control systems
31 [26], [27]. Electric light fluctuations due to daylight variability are especially
32 problematic when switching systems are installed [26]. Certainly, when the
33 intensity of collected sunlight is very high, these daylight-linked control sys-
34 tems are not valid. This statement has not been studied.
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38 The intensity of collected sunlight changes systematically, the most rapid
39 changes occurring during twilight. The intensity decreases as dusk falls and
40 increases as dawn breaks as a function of the height of the Sun. These
41 fluctuations in the intensity of collected sunlight can cause glare, insufficient
42 light and non-uniformity in illuminance levels. These daylight fluctuations
43 are caused by variations of the cloud cover or by movement of the solar
44 collector.
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47 The variability in solar radiation and irradiance transitions caused by
48 the shadows of moving clouds are essential parameters in determining the
49 response time required by the system. These parameters have been studied,
50 for example, in [28], [29]. The apparent velocity of clouds produces falls and
51 rises in irradiance on the solar collector. Lappalainen et al. [30] shows that
52 the average speed is 8.7 and 8.4 (m/s) for the falls and the rises, respectively.
53 The lengths of irradiance transitions caused by the edges of moving clouds
54 are typically around 100 (m) [30]. Therefore, the average angular velocity of
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9 the clouds, with regard to the solar luminaire, is 0.087 and 0.084 (rad/s) for
10 falls and the rises, respectively.

11 These daylight fluctuations can be produced by a high or low intensity of
12 collected sunlight. The proposed system solves this problem in two different
13 ways: it will reduce the intensity of collected sunlight by driving a stepper
14 motor when the intensity of collected sunlight is very high, and will sup-
15 plement natural light with an electric lamp when the intensity of collected
16 sunlight decreases. A good lighting control must quickly compensate these
17 fluctuations, maintaining a constant level of illuminance [31].

18 Previous studies have analyzed the factors influencing occupant visual
19 comfort:

20 (i) The human eye is less sensitive to extremely gradual changes and is
21 fairly sensitive to more rapid changes [32].

22 (ii) The human eye is able to continuously adapt itself to the change of
23 light, but a repeated change of light within a short interval causes eye fatigue
24 and visual discomfort [27].

25 The time between two consecutive daylight adjustments and the fluctu-
26 ation entity [27], are two factors that need to be taken into account in the
27 design of the control system.

28 Hence, the aim of this study is to design a daylight fluctuations con-
29 trol capable of gradually compensating the variability in solar radiation and
30 irradiance transitions.

31 2.2. Elements of the daylight fluctuations control

32 A hybrid lighting system comprises a combination of electrical and natural
33 light sources at each individual workstation. The system has to be able to
34 produce a uniform source of light using natural light, electrical light, or both
35 sources. This control system is developed to ensure that the combination of
36 daylighting and electrical lighting maintains a uniform lighting level.

steady?

37 The main components of the proposed daylight fluctuations control are:
38 the luminaire, mirror, shaft, frame, stepper motor driver, stepper motor, light
39 sensor, limit switch, XBee and microcontroller. The mirror is mounted on a
40 frame made of a thermoplastic material, being fixed on the frame using an
41 industrial adhesive. The frame was manufactured using a 3D printer. The
42 rotation shaft comprises a carbon steel bar. All these elements are located on
43 the ceiling. The structure of the newly developed solar luminaire control is
44 shown in Fig. 2. The sunlight transmitted via optical fiber is reflected onto
45 a mirror. This mirror is rotated between 0 and 90° by means of a stepper

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motor. This direct solar radiation is directed to the light dispersion element so as to distribute the light evenly. The stepper motor driver can adjust the natural illumination level. The dimmable electronic ballast can adjust the artificial illumination level in the presence or absence of natural light. The luminaire is a diffuser, similar in shape to a downlight.

This control system can be integrated in a smart lighting system in which several hybrid solar luminaires are used. For this reason, a wireless technology solution is chosen as a connectivity option.

Fig. 2. Schematic of a solar luminaire control.

Fig. 3 shows several photographs of the prototype.

where is the mirror ?

Fig. 3. Photographs of the prototype.

2.3. Daylight fluctuation control algorithms

The algorithm has to fulfil the following conditions:

(i) If the light level is higher than the predefined value, the stepper motor starts to rotate to reduce the natural light level and the electric lamp is turned off.

(ii) If the light level is lower than the predefined value, the electric lamp is controlled according to the availability of daylight in order to supplement natural light during cloudy periods.

The algorithm is shown in Fig. 4. The following is an analysis of each of the blocks.

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Fig. 4. Control algorithm of the proposed hybrid solar luminaire control.

2.3.1. Mirror movement control

The position of the mirror can be adjusted using two movements (clockwise direction and anticlockwise direction). Therefore, a stepper motor and stepper motor driver are used for the movements of the mirror. The stepper motor can adjust the level of natural illumination. The driver supplies appropriate control signals and supply voltage to the associated stepper motor. The microcontroller is responsible for the stepper motor, which rotates according to the required direction and stepping number. The stepper motor motion is described as follows:

(i) If the light level is higher than the predefined value, the stepper motor begins to run clockwise. Thus, the mirror is driven step by step in the clockwise direction. With the increase in the step number, the light level decreases.

(ii) After a while, the current value is compared again to the previous value of the light level. If this new value is still higher than the previous one, the stepper motor continues to run clockwise.

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(iii) When this condition is no longer fulfilled, the stepper motor begins to run anticlockwise. Thus, the mirror is driven step by step in the anticlockwise direction. The stepper motor will stop at the starting position.

The algorithm can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Control algorithm of the mirror movement control.

2.3.2. Initial mirror position

The initial position of the mirror is the position in which the system delivers the highest amount of solar luminous flux. In this position, the mirror forms a certain angle with a horizontal plane. This angle is shown in Section 3. This position is determined by a limit switch. The stepper motor motion is described as follows: if the limit switch signal is not equal to 1, the stepper motor begins to run anticlockwise. Thus, the mirror is driven step by step in the anticlockwise direction until the limit switch signal is equal to 1. The algorithm is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Control algorithm of the initial mirror position.

3. Results and discussion

The purpose of this experimental phase, carried out in the laboratory, was to verify the feasibility and applicability of the proposed daylight fluctuations control. The experiment was conducted in a test box in order to measure the illuminance values provided by the hybrid lighting system. The test box is a pre-fabricated box measuring 575 (mm) long, 575 (mm) wide and 498 (mm) in height. In order to avoid reflection from the inner walls of the test box, all its surfaces were covered with black matte fabric with a reflectance value lower than 0.1. The ceiling of the test box was painted black, with a matte paint with a reflectance value of approximately 0.1. The zero illuminance value inside the test box was verified in order to obtain precise measurements with the solar luminaire and the electric lamp. Illuminance values were measured by a light sensor, the characteristics of which are summarized in this section. The solar luminaire and electric lamp were mounted in the upper part of the test box, while the light sensor was placed at the bottom. The

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9 horizontal distance between the light sensor and the center of the diffuser is
10 175 (*mm*), approximately.

11 A portable fiber optic light source was used in all the experimental tests.
12 Different step angles were employed for each test.

13 Problems with this daylight fluctuations control occur when the intensity
14 of collected sunlight is very high. In this case, the amount of light emitted
15 by the solar luminaire needs to be reduced. Fig. 7 shows the different
16 illuminance values, obtained with a constant luminous flux, for different step
17 angles (1.80° , 1.44° , 1.08° , 0.72° , 0.36°) of the stepper motor. Some precision
18 motors are able to make 1000 steps in one revolution, with a step angle
19 of 0.36° . A standard motor will have a step angle of 1.8° , with 200 steps
20 per revolution. The initial mirror position corresponds to the maximum
21 illuminance value.
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23 Each time a command pulse is received, one step is taken. This value is
24 one second, as the duration of irradiance transitions varies a lot, from one
25 second up to several minutes [28].
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27 Each graph in Fig. 7 is composed of two sides, separated by the maximum
28 illuminance value. On the left side of the graph, the position of the mirror
29 varies from 0° to the initial mirror position. Conversely, on the right side of
30 the graph, the position of the mirror varies from the initial mirror position
31 up to 90° . Each of these sides has different slopes. The slope of the left
32 side of the graph is lower, so the variation of the illuminance will be more
33 gradual. Obviously, the more the step angle decreases, the more the slope
34 decreases.
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Fig. 7. Relationship between illuminance values and number of steps.

Our dimming profile is the relationship between the daylight output level (in percentage values with respect to the illuminance of the initial mirror position) and the mirror position, in percentage values. To obtain the dimming profile of each side of the curve, the values have been adjusted to a 2nd-order polynomial. Table 1 shows the values of R^2 . The best results are obtained with the left side of the graph. Fig. 8 shows the dimming profiles for the left side.

Table 1. Values of R^2 for the dimming profiles.

Step angle ($^\circ$)	Left side	Right side
1.80	0.9921	0.9794
1.44	0.9960	0.9863
1.08	0.9967	0.9942
0.72	0.9958	0.9877
0.36	0.9968	0.9848

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Fig. 8. Dimming profiles for different step angles (Left side).

An artificial lighting system consists of a dimmer, a driver and a luminaire. The combination of dimmer and driver is different in the workings of the human eye. The human eye does not perceive changes in light level in a linear manner. Human vision operates according to a logarithmic function [34], which can be approximated to a square function [35]. The perceived brightness is approximated by the following equation:

$$\text{Perceived Brightness} \simeq \sqrt[2]{\text{Measured Brightness}} \quad (1)$$

The aim is to achieve a perceived linear dimming, so that the perceived changes in brightness may be discerned. In other words, the brightness of the light must be matched to the way our eyes behave. To obtain the perceived dimming profiles, the dimming profiles are used in conjunction with equation (1). Fig. 9 shows the comparison between dimming profiles.

relevant for this study?

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Fig. 9. Dimming profiles comparison.

Fig. 10 shows the different dimming profiles perceived for different step angles (left side). As shown in this figure, all dimming profiles perceived have a linear zone, which is curved as the mirror position decreases.

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Fig. 10. Different dimming profiles perceived.

Human eye is less sensitive to extremely gradual changes. Table 2 shows the number of steps in the linear zone for each dimming profile perceived (left and right side).

Table 2. Number of steps in dimming profile perceived with a linear dimming range.

Step angle (°)	Left side	Right side
1.80	10	7
1.44	12	8
1.08	19	10
0.72	24	18
0.36	59	33

Another indicator that has been considered is the Just Noticeable Difference (*JND*). The *JND* is the illuminance difference of a given target under given viewing conditions that the average observer can just perceive. The total *JND* steps for the eye is about 1000, while the total *JND* steps for fixed adaptation is about 200 [36]. Table 3 shows the maximum *JND*.

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Table 3. Maximum just noticeable difference.

Step angle ($^{\circ}$)	<i>JND</i>	
	Left side	Right side
1.80	165	149
1.44	102	196
1.08	75	138
0.72	75	69
0.36	65	58

Several studies have demonstrated that occupants prefer to have control over lighting [37], [38]. This is because the visual comfort of each occupant depends on “human factors” [39]. Therefore, the choice of the suitable step angle is subjective, being an appreciation of the occupant. From the point of view of gradual changes, a step angle of 0.36° is the best. From the point of view of the *JND*, all the step angles are below 200.

4. Daylight fluctuations control implementation

The proposed daylight fluctuations control has been conceived as a combined architecture embedding sensing elements (light sensor, limit switch) and actuators (stepper motor drive, electronic dimmable ballast) that are managed by a dedicated control unit. This control unit is implemented by means of a microcontroller. The microcontroller has the following functions: to collect data from sensors (light sensor, limit switch), to drive actuators (stepper motor drive, electronic dimmable ballast) and to transfer information (*XBee*).

The daylight fluctuations control continuously monitors the level of light (light sensor), which includes light from both the daylight source and an electric lamp. The changes in the light level of the electric lamp due to fluctuations in the intensity of collected sunlight are continuously transmitted to the control system.

4.1. Hardware specification

Fig. 11 provides photographs of the hardware specification of the daylight fluctuations control.

Fig. 11. Photographs of the hardware prototype.

4.1.1. Microcontroller

The daylight fluctuations control is based on an Arduino Mini [40]. The Arduino Mini is used because of its low cost, compact size, compatibility and easy interfacing. The Arduino Mini is a small microcontroller board based on the ATmega 328. It has 14 digital input/output pins (6 of which can be used as PWM outputs), 8 analog inputs and a 16 MHz crystal oscillator. It can be programmed using the USB Serial adapter or another *USB* or *RS232* to *TTL* serial adapter. The Arduino Mini has the following inputs: light sensor and limit switch; and the following outputs: stepper motor driver, electronic dimmable ballast and Xbee.

4.1.2. Light sensor

The task of the light sensor is to maintain the lamp at a certain illuminance level at each individual workstation. A *BH1750* can be used for

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9 this purpose. This sensor is an ambient light intensity sensor. The break-
10 out board has a built-in 16-bit A2D converter that can directly provide a
11 digital output signal. The output from the sensor is in Lux (Lx) and does
12 not require advanced calculations in the sketch. The *BH1750* communicates
13 using the I²C Protocol. It is possible to detect a wide range at High resolu-
14 tion (1 – 65535 lx). The resolution is a 1 (lx). The light sensor has three
15 terminals, V_{DC} , ground and output signal. Its features are: power supply
16 $V_{DC\max} = 4.5$ (V), current supply $I_{max} = 7$ (mA).

20 4.1.3. Limit switch

21 Its features are: power supply $V_{AC\max} = 250$ (V), current supply $I_{max} =$
22 15 (A).

25 4.1.4. Stepper motor

26 A stepper motor with the step angle variable has been used. The stepper
27 motor is a *28BYJ – 48 – 5V*. The *28BYJ – 48* is a small, low-cost stepper
28 motor suitable for a large range of applications. Its features are: power
29 supply $V = 5$ (V), current supply $I = 83$ (mA).

32 4.1.5. Stepper motor driver

33 One stepper motor driver is dedicated to the sole stepper motor. The
34 driver supplies appropriate control signals and supply voltage to the associ-
35 ated step motor, so that the step motor rotates in the appropriate direction
36 (clockwise direction or anticlockwise direction) and the number of steps re-
37 quested by the microcontroller. The step motor driver is a *ULN2003*.

41 4.1.6. XBee

42 There are various connectivity solutions for a smart lighting system.
43 Wireless networks are usually preferred. The most popular wireless tech-
44 nologies used are Wi-Fi, Bluetooth and ZigBee. ZigBee is usually preferred
45 due to its low cost and low power consumption.

46
47 The *XBee* module is a technology for wireless communication among mul-
48 tiple devices in a Wireless Personal Area Network. *XBee* modules are embed-
49 ded solutions that provide wireless end-point connectivity to devices. This
50 module is a standard for wireless communication based on the *IEEE802.15.4*
51 protocol. The *XBee* module is equipped with an on-chip antenna provided
52 by Digi-MaxStream [41]. The transmission capabilities (ranges, consump-
53 tion, etc.) are shown in [41]. These transmission capabilities have been
54 widely tested and provide optimal performances [42].

4.1.7. DC-to-DC converter

The electronic dimmable ballast has input voltage values of $(1 - 10V_{DC})$. A *PWM* output of the Arduino Mini $(0 - 5V_{DC})$ and a DC-to-DC converter are used to obtain this power range.

The proposed daylight fluctuations control included the use of a fluorescent lamp as the electric lamp. The rated values of the electric lamp, taken from the manufacturer's catalog, are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Rated values of commercial lamps [33].

Lamp type	Wattage (W)	Lumens	Rated life (h)
Fluorescent lamp (FL)	6	280	10000

4.2. Cost analysis

The total cost of the implemented daylight fluctuations control with an integrated controller and wireless module is calculated and presented in Table 5. The cost of the microcontroller, integrated sensors and stepper motor is 18.51% of the overall cost of the system. The cost of the downlight, mirror and shaft subassembly is 28.42% of the total cost of the system. The cost of the wireless module is 40.49% of the total cost of the system. The wireless module represents a high percentage of the total cost. This module could be removed when the solar luminaire works autonomously. Should this be the case, data on the solar luminaire would no longer be necessary.

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Table 5. Cost of the daylight fluctuations control.

Item	Unit cost (€)	Quantity	Cost (€)
Arduino mini pro	3.25	1	3.25
Light sensor (BH1750)	2.90	1	2.90
Limit switch	0.20	1	0.20
4K7 resistor	0.20	2	0.40
7K5 resistor	0.15	1	0.15
10K resistor	0.1	1	0.1
1K resistor	0.05	1	0.05
ka7810 voltage regulator	0.13	1	0.13
BC639 transistor	0.03	1	0.03
0.33 μF capacitor	0.5	1	0.5
0.1 μF capacitor	0.8	1	0.8
28BYJ-48-5V Stepper motor + ULN2003	1.60	1	1.60
XBee module S1	16.95	1	16.95
Mirror	0.9	1	0.9
Shaft + frame	5	1	5
Downlight	6	1	6
PCB cost	2.9	1	2.9
Total			41.86

5. Conclusions

This paper presents a new daylight fluctuations control especially conceived for enclosed spaces with no access to daylight from side openings. When the intensity of solar irradiance is very high the different daylight-linked control systems are not valid. This system is based on a low cost microcontroller. It also allows communication between each hybrid solar luminaire and a main controller. This communication is based on a long-range wireless solution. Therefore, this control system can be integrated in a smart lighting system in which several hybrid solar luminaires are used.

Laboratory tests on the daylight fluctuations control have shown positive results. At the end of the experimental laboratory tests, the main results comprise: (i) its functionality and applicability to real cases; (ii) its low cost; (iii) the fact that its different dimming profiles, perceived with different step

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9 angles, have a linear zone, as a result of which the perceived changes in
10 brightness are correct; (iv) the fact that, for gradual changes, a step angle of
11 0.36° is the best; and (v) its Just Noticeable Difference is less than 200 for
12 any step angle used.
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14 With regard to possible future work, the possibility exists of studying the
15 use of this daylight fluctuations control integrated in a smart lighting system
16 in applications such as multi-floor office buildings or underground railway
17 stations, among others.
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